

TRAINING ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM.

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Abstract: Preschool education experts agree that the creation and implementation of innovative ideas in the educational system is a necessary condition for the development of a modern kindergarten. In connection with financing, the inclusion of innovative organizational solutions in the daily routine of state institutions "When money goes to a preschool teacher" significantly increases the reputation of the institution and determines the further directions of development. The introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process, taking into account the psychophysical age characteristics, is always positively perceived by preschool teachers, they easily change activities.

Key words: preschool education system, child psychology, education, modern technologies, innovations, development, innovative technologies.

The economic power of each country, the rise in the level of social and spiritual life is determined by the competitiveness of the educational system and the development of science. Therefore, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority is to fundamentally improve the education sector, increase the quality of education, form a generation with intellectual potential, physical fitness, in-depth training of specific sciences and training of qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy. were defined as tasks, and it was planned to create an educational system that could ultimately meet the demands of today's era. Game technologies form the basis of education for preschool children. Since the leading activity of children of this age is play, it is implemented as an educational technology. The basis of the use of game technologies is the activity and imagination of children. According to the studies of scientists, the game is one of the main types of activity together with work and study. The game is defined as a type of activity in situations aimed at mastering and re-creating social experiences, and in it the control of the individual's behavior is formed and improved.

As a result of reforms in the field, the management mechanism in the preschool education system was fundamentally improved, the non-state educational service provision system was reformed, the secondary special, vocational education system was revised, the quality of training of highly educated specialists was improved.

improvement measures were strengthened, a two-level system of post-university education was introduced. The traditional way of education, which believes that its main task is to provide a certain amount of knowledge, is completely inadequate to prepare young people who can live in a rapidly changing world. Because science and technology have developed to such an extent that now a person cannot keep even the most basic concepts in his memory. Moreover, if the young people who are taking an independent step into the life of constant changes are not ready for such changes both intellectually and spiritually, they may not find their place in the world of competition. Nowadays, rich experiences have been accumulated in the educational system. For example, business games, computer-based training, individualized training, humanitarianism, cooperation, personal training, etc.

In turn, the initiative pedagogical composition Parent community, the need to improve the mechanisms of interaction of kindergarten students with their families is also important. Experts say that innovative technologies in the states are not only possible, but also necessary. However, it should be remembered that pedagogical technologies can be used in the educational process of preschool children, given several strict requirements. These include:

- Conceptuality means that the learning process should be based on a certain scientific understanding.
- Technologies belonging to the system, these technologies must have all the characteristics of the system. That is, they must be integral, logical and their elements must be components - interrelated.
- Processing - the pedagogical team should understand the possibility of setting certain goals, planning the educational process, correcting one or another moment during the work process.
- Reproducibility - the technology should be equally effective regardless of the individual teacher applied to the requirement.

Therefore, innovative technologies in preschool education are connected with game technologies. But they cannot be considered the same. Because innovations are used in different directions. A pedagogue of a preschool educational organization should have effective (subject-oriented), cost-effective (person-oriented), cooperation technologies for the principled implementation of his activities. An experienced creative pedagogue can create his own technology of "authorship" based on these methods. In this, he is motivated by his previously acquired knowledge and formed worldview. If we look at the history of the emergence of innovative pedagogical technologies, the bank of ideas has played an important role in their introduction into

the educational process. For example, the Italian doctor Maria Montessori, although her profession was not related to education, she implemented a unique educational method through her rich thinking. "The method is based on the axiom that each child is unique and requires a special approach to education. The education system consists of three parts: the teacher, the child and the environment," says his teaching.

Since preschool children are in the period of understanding through visual imagination, all new knowledge is based on visualization. Educators effectively use interactive methods as innovative pedagogical technologies with children of this age. Because by using these methods, every child can show their individual abilities; playing logical games has a great positive effect on the child's mental development; helps to form clear ideas about environmental phenomena; serves to develop the child both mentally and physically; sets children a goal and teaches them to realize it; teaches to find a solution to the problem independently when difficult situations arise. At the same time, it is possible to form the ability to freely express one's opinion in order to improve children's speech fluency.

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